

Refractory lining challenges in transitioning from established to hydrogen-ready operations in DRI shaft furnace technologies

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Direct Reduced Iron (DRI) is a well-established iron-ore reduction technology crucial for the decarbonization of the iron and steel sector, which accounts for approximately 8 % of the world's energy demand and 7–9 % of global anthropogenic CO₂ emissions. Industry-wide efforts to reduce these emissions include optimizing and adapting current production processes for energy and material savings, carbon capture and storage, recycling, and alternative fuels. One significant alternative is to leverage over 70 years of expertise in DRI technologies, offering potential emission reductions up to 97 % when compared to the blast furnace route. To this end, leading original equipment manufacturers (OEMs) in DRI shaft furnace technologies are developing processes that incorporate increased hydrogen content in their process gas composition, which may require revising refractory lining concepts within these units. Refractory providers share the responsibility to support relevant OEMs, iron and steelmakers in their transition from traditional blast furnace route to either established DRI processes or future fully hydrogen-ready DRI shaft furnaces. Current wear mechanisms have been analyzed, along with expected changes as hydrogen content increases in the process.

KEYWORDS: IRON MAKING, DRI, HYDROGEN, REFRACTORIES, DECARBONIZATION, GREEN STEEL, WEAR MECHANISMS, NET ZERO, SHAFT FURNACE;

INTRODUCTION

The primary strategy for reducing CO₂ emissions in steelmaking is to explore alternatives to the traditional coal-based blast furnace and basic oxygen furnace routes. Established methods in this context include coal-based and natural gas (NG)-based direct reduced iron (DRI) production processes [1] [2]. Even with the high CO₂ emissions associated with coal-based DRI using rotary kilns, there is a potential CO₂ emission reduction of 38 % [1]. The predominant DRI technology which employs a reducing gas mixture of methane (CH₄), hydrogen (H₂), and carbon monoxide (CO) in a shaft furnace process, known as NG-based DRI, can reduce CO₂ emissions by up to 61 %. Increasing the hydrogen (H₂) content in the reducing atmosphere further enhances CO₂ emission savings, with emerging fully hydrogen-ready (up to 100 %) shaft furnace DRI units, promising up to 97 % CO₂ reduction [1]. Consequently, there is a growing number of ongoing and announced projects for natural gas and hydrogen-based DRI shaft furnace units worldwide. Currently, over 70 % of the global DRI production utilize shaft furnace techno-

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logies [2]. More than 15 direct reduction plants, all shaft furnace units, with annual capacities ranging from 1.0 to 2.5 million tonnes per annum (Mtpa) are scheduled to be commissioned between 2024 and 2030 [3].

The DRI Shaft Furnace

The shaft furnace is the principal equipment in a DRI plant, where the reduction of the iron ore pellets occurs. These furnaces typically have a height of about 20 meters and a diameter of 5 to 7 meters, with size being one of the key parameters related to production capacity. Inside the furnace, the iron ore undergoes reduction, achieving typical metallization levels between 92 % and 96 % [4]. Iron ore pellets are introduced from the top of the furnace and descend through the shaft furnace while the process gas mixture, primarily composed of H_2 and CO , flows upward, counter-current to the pellets. The reduction reactions convert iron oxides into metallic iron, leaving a porous, sponge-like structure in the pellet.

The main zones in a DRI Shaft Furnace are:

- Preheating Zone: where the iron ore pellets are preheated before moving into the reduction zone.
- Reduction Zone: where the reduction reactions happen, using a gas mixture of H_2 and CO at temperatures

just below 1000 °C.

- Cooling Zone: where reduced pellets cool down before being discharged. Some units allow for hot discharge, facilitating a direct connection to the EAF, thus increasing overall energy savings.

Due to the temperature and pressure, the shaft furnace and all related ducts are typically protected with a refractory lining. The material selection for each zone is usually based on specific wear mechanisms and operational parameters, often using mid- to high-alumina refractories [5]. Different wear mechanisms can act together, but typically one is predominant depending on the location within the furnace. Additionally, heat transfer is considered to ensure the process achieves a certain level of energy efficiency. The main wear mechanisms of the refractory lining include reduction of the oxides by H_2 and CO in the process gas, abrasion, thermal shock and mechanical stresses.

Wear of Refractory Lining in an NG-based DRI shaft furnace: Post-Mortem Analysis

Samples taken from an NG-based DRI shaft furnace have shown signs of the mentioned wear mechanisms. In the reduction zone, analyzed samples exhibit a certain degree of reduction at the hot face (Fig. 1).

Fig.1 -a) Cut sample of a refractory brick taken from the reduction zone, b) Scanning Electron Microscopy image of the hot face of the analyzed refractory brick: the outermost part has lost its glassy phase, revealing a residual mullite network from the fireclay, with the mullite remaining unaffected (see red arrows).

Analyses revealed reductions in silica, iron oxide, and phosphorus pentoxide, particularly at the hot face of the refractory brick. Upon reduction, SiO₂ forms gaseous SiO and H₂O or CO₂. Typical observations related to SiO₂ reduction are weight loss or enrichment of SiO₂ at the cold face and Al₂O₃ at the hot face. Additionally, iron oxides may be reduced to metallic iron, leading to possible weight loss and/or the formation of metal droplets. The analyzed samples show a progressive decrease in reduction from the hot face towards the interior of the

lining. Tab. 1 summarizes the changes in the chemical composition of main oxides in the analyzed refractory brick. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) investigations of the reduction zone indicate that SiO₂ in the glassy phase is attacked before SiO₂ in the mineral phase (Fig. 1). Microscopical inspection using SEM combined with Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS) confirmed this behavior, reinforcing that the reduction of these oxides predominantly occurs on the hot face (Tab. 1).

Tab.1 - Evolution of the chemical composition through the analyzed refractory brick thickness.

Refractory Component	30 – 100 μm from Interface	10 mm from Interface	18 mm from Interface
	Weight %		
Al ₂ O ₃	45.3	44.0	42.6
SiO ₂	48.9	50.3	52.0
Fe ₂ O ₃	2.0	1.4	1.2
P ₂ O ₅	0.8	1.7	1.4

Other possible mechanisms within a DRI unit include abrasion and thermal shock. Abrasion involves the mechanical removal of the refractory material due to ore throughput and dust carried by process gas. The fluid dynamics inside a DRI shaft furnace determine the wear pattern; however, the general abrasion resistance of the refractory lining can be enhanced by selecting appropriate raw materials and binders. For example, the density of a refractory brick significantly influences its overall abrasion resistance. Thermal shock typically occurs in zones exposed to temperature changes, potentially leading to

premature spalling. Sudden temperature gradients can compromise the structural integrity of the refractory material, impacting its overall mechanical properties. This wear mechanism can affect the refractory lining, especially when inadequate materials are chosen for these zones. Observations of samples from these regions have shown a roughened hot face surface, indicating that abrasion is predominant over reduction (Fig. 2), which is expected since the process gas in these locations has already started to react with the iron ore pellets, having less reduction capability and lower temperatures.

Fig.2 -Cut sample of a refractory brick taken from area between reduction and cooling zone showing abrasive wear.

Residual properties have also been measured in post-mortem samples. Achieved average values have shown that the main mechanical properties have remained intact, but the thermal shock resistance is decreased, particularly in bricks exposed to temperature cycling (Tab. 2).

Tab. 2 - Average residual properties of the refractory lining samples.

Property	Unit	Reduction Zone	Mechanical and Thermal Wear Zone	As Produced
Bulk Density (ISO 5017)	g/cm ³	2.32	2.30	2.32
Apparent Porosity (ISO 5017)	Vol %	14.5	15.8	16.0
Cold Crushing Strength (ISO 10059-1)	MPa	55	44	55
Abrasion Resistance (ASTM C704)	cm ³	11	13	< 20
Thermal Shock Resistance (DIN EN 993-11)	Nr. of Cycles	30	11	25

Plant owners highly value well-designed refractory linings with comprehensive material selection to avoid frequent maintenance needs, which can cause productivity losses and increase operational costs.

The Future DRI Process

The shift towards a 100 % hydrogen-operated reduction process necessitates an understanding of its impact on the refractory lining, potentially requiring adaptations in refractory material selection to avoid compromising the furnace's lifespan. All refractory oxides can theoretically react with hydrogen [6] [7]. When H₂ is the sole reducing agent, water vapor is the only by-product, rendering the process carbon-free. Internal calculations of thermodynamic stability of major refractory oxides show resistance

to reduction in the following order: ZrO₂ > Al₂O₃ > 3AlO₃ - 2SiO₂ > CaO > SiO₂ > Fe₂O₃ > P₂O₅. Notably, ZrO₂ and Al₂O₃ are almost inert in a 100 % H₂ atmosphere.

Alumina-silica refractories with are commonly used in DRI Shaft Furnaces, balancing economic considerations and effective lining performance.

FactSage 8.1 simulations of the reduction of SiO₂ by pure H₂ under thermodynamic equilibrium indicate minimal silica reduction up to approximately 1000 °C (Tab. 3). The reduction increases with temperature, in line with observations from testing.

Tab. 3 - Comparison of weight loss from thermodynamic simulations and refractory exposure to 100% H₂ at 1 bar pressure at various temperatures. Column (a): SiO₂ weight losses according to thermodynamic simulations. Column (b): weight losses of two alumina-silica refractories and an insulating brick after 200 hours of H₂ exposure.

Temperature (oC)	a- Calculated weight % of reacted SiO ₂	b- Weight loss % of exposed bricks (100% H ₂ , 1 bar, 200 hrs, 200L/h H ₂)		
		Fireclay	Andalusite	28 Grade
800	0.0002			
1000	0.01	0.6	0.1	0.04
1200	0.3	5.1	2.1	11.1

Three ceramic-bonded alumina silica bricks, namely dense fireclay, dense andalusite and a 28 grade insulation brick, were exposed to a gas flow of 100 % H₂, for 100 and 200 hrs at 1000 °C and 1200 °C in an electric furnace (Tab. 3, Tab. 4). In all cases, the relative weight loss significantly exceeded the calculated weight loss of SiO₂. Considering the sum of oxides more easily reduced by H₂ compared to SiO₂, all tested bricks exhibited three to ten times higher weight losses than expected from simulations,

indicating SiO₂ reduction. Consistent with the discussion on silica reduction at the hot face of a refractory brick in the reduction zone of a NG-based shaft furnace, the fireclay brick demonstrated a higher weight loss than the andalusite brick due to its greater amount of glassy phase. The example of the insulating brick illustrates that in addition to chemical and mineralogical composition, other refractory material characteristics like porosity also play a crucial role.

Tab. 4 - Chemical composition of tested bricks prior to hydrogen exposure.

Characteristics	Fireclay Brick	Andalusite Brick	28 Grade Brick
Bulk Density (g/cm ³)	2.23	2.52	0.94
SiO ₂	52.0	38.6	32.0
Fe ₂ O ₃	1.4	1.00	0.7
P ₂ O ₅	0.5	0	0.1

In addition, the reduction of refractory oxides by H₂ depends on gas velocities, operating temperature and pressure. For example, the weight losses of fireclay and andalusite bricks after exposure to pure H₂ at a flow rate of 100 L/h were ten times lower compared to experiments conducted at a 200 L/h H₂ gas flow.

To investigate the impact of hydrogen reduction on refractory properties, high alumina refractory bricks with 88

% to 92 % Al₂O₃ content (Tab. 5), based on different raw materials and binders, have been exposed to a 100 % H₂ atmosphere for 200 hours at 1200 °C. The main properties were measured before and after testing. Generally, it was observed that bulk density and cold modulus of rupture tend to decrease, while porosity increases under these conditions.

Tab. 5 - Property variations after exposure to 100 % H₂ at 1200 °C and 1 bar for 200 hrs.

Property	Brick A		Brick B		Brick C	
	Prior H ₂ exposure	After H ₂ exposure	Prior H ₂ exposure	After H ₂ exposure	Prior H ₂ exposure	After H ₂ exposure
Cold Modulus of Rupture (ISO 5014, MPa)	18.0	10.5	12.0	7.0	8.9	5.6
Bulk Density (ISO 5017, g/cm ³)	2.93	2.78	3.11	3.03	3.04	3.05
Apparent Porosity (ISO 5017, %)	15.7	23.9	14.8	17.4	17.5	16.9
Weight Loss (%)	- 4.5		- 1.5		- 0.4	

Transitioning to hydrogen-based DRI units necessitates a comprehensive understanding of the wear mechanisms affecting the refractory materials under future process conditions. Ongoing research is actively focused on quantifying and evaluating the behavior of refractories as a function of various process parameters. This research aims to optimize the refractory lining performance in emerging DRI technologies. Primary wear mechanisms, including oxides' reduction by hydrogen, need to be thoroughly understood to provide sufficient technical information for the OEMs and lining designers to perform proper material selection.

areas exposed to hydrogen at elevated temperatures. The selection of refractory materials should consider the potential for reduction by hydrogen, as changes in key properties may accelerate other wear mechanisms, such as abrasion and thermal shock. Further investigations are needed to deepen our understanding of property variations under long-term operational conditions in atmospheres with increased hydrogen content. This includes examining the influence of the reduction of silica, iron oxide, and phosphorus pentoxide on the overall properties and performance of the lining.

SUMMARY

Future DRI processes will increasingly rely on higher hydrogen ratios in the process gas. Particular attention must be given to the design of the refractory lining in

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